

**PEDAGOGICAL ART OF TRADITIONAL SINGING AS WELL
THE PLACE OF THE SINGER'S VOICE IN IT**

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Annotation: This article provides detailed information about the national singing art and its teaching pedagogy. There were also comments on the national art of singing, as well as women's voices in shashmaqom and their performance.

Keywords: national singing, shashmaqom, voice, timbre, pedagogy, women's voice, scientific research, cultural reform

The art of national status, which is an integral part of the cultural heritage of our people, occupies an important place in our spiritual life with its ancient history, deep philosophical roots, unique artistic style and rich creative traditions. Over the centuries, this unique art, which has been polished by the hard work and dedication of great poets and scientists, skilled composers, hafiz and musicians, and creative thinking, has gained great fame and attention not only in our country and eastern countries, but also on a global scale. The fact that "Shashmaqom", which is the culmination of the art of maqam, was recognized by UNESCO as an intangible cultural heritage of humanity and included in its representative list is a clear confirmation of this. During the past period, certain works were carried out in our country to study and develop the art of status. In particular, the publication of the sheet music of the Uzbek "Shashmaqom" and the recording of maqam songs on magnetic tapes in accordance with them was an event of great scientific and cultural importance. It should be noted that currently in our country the Maqom Ensemble named after Yunus Rajabi, Maqom ensembles in the

regions, a special department in this direction is operating at the State Conservatory of Uzbekistan, and scientific research is being conducted in this field.[1]

At the same time, the vast possibilities of maqam art are not being used enough to realize our national identity, to develop our culture in all aspects, to educate our people, especially our young generation, in the spirit of high human feelings, to form their aesthetic taste and thinking. In this direction, in-depth scientific-theoretical research, creation of educational and methodical literature, promotion of the art of status through radio and television, mass media, Internet network in our country and abroad, teachers of status, scientists of the field and the work of materially and morally supporting the activities of specialists, talented and promising young performers has been neglected. A characteristic feature of statuses is to ensure the achievement of mental perfection by consciously mastering all aspects of spiritual virtue based on mental depth and logical thinking. The scope of folk songs and statuses is not limited. Including these examples of performance in textbooks according to the age characteristics of students, worldview, level of moral-aesthetic development will increase the morale of students during the educational process. Currently, the main goal of musical education in educational institutions is to ensure that the young generation grows up in the spirit of respect for our national musical heritage. According to the experts, our people have been enjoying the elegant and heart-felt, deep philosophical meaning of the classical maqam songs with impressive instruments since ancient times. The fact that maqams have survived for centuries is closely related to a number of factors, in particular, the high performance skills of teachers and musicians. Performance practice is the criterion that reflects the live process of folk music art. The more advanced and potential performance practice is, the greater its impact on creativity will be.[2]

Concept of classical music, melodies, songs, Shashmaqom, types of status are described. Each topic is given examples of performance for listening and singing based on the age characteristics of children. In the process of studying the textbook topics, many comments and problems were identified regarding the practice of singing. In the music textbook of grade VI, each quarter aims to cover a specific topic. Students will get theoretical information about Shashmaqom, Chormaqom, and Khorezm executive schools during the quarters. However, performance examples are not provided to acquire skills and competences in singing status songs. The main reason for this is that the song samples in these status performance schools consist of works with a large diapason, which require high performance skills. That's why the authors decided to give the works. When choosing songs according to the students' age characteristics, worldview, level of moral-aesthetic development, there are many examples of oasis song performance - works at the level of classical songs. For example, folk songs "Sharob", "Tanovar", "Miskinlar", "Farganacha", works of past composers "Solim", "Dilkhuroj", "Sallamno", dozens of classical songs. Among them are the songs "Chorgoh 4", "Kashkarcha", "Rock", "Sarohbori", "Dugoh 2-3". It is necessary to include the full version of these songs in the textbooks in order to make the young generation a mature person capable of perceiving our national musical heritage. After theoretical knowledge of the subject, musical literacy and performance works should be logically appropriate to the subject. For example, in the textbook, an understanding of classical music is given, and in the music literacy section, the process of conducting exercises that do not correspond to the topic is transferred. Based on the psycho-physiological conditions of children, it is necessary to choose both musical literacy and singing in accordance with the topic, without distracting the child's memory with three

different activities during the one-hour lesson.[3]

In the music literacy section, it would be appropriate if key words or terms related to classical music, maqam, bozgoy, maqam names, etc. were given. The introduction of classic tunes "Ferganacha Janon", "O Sarviravon", "Sarohbori Dogohtaronalari", "Qalandar", "Sokinoma" and "Uforlar" in the hymn section increases the effectiveness of the lesson. We cannot say that all music teachers have excellent performance skills. not all teachers are talented singers or musicians. Therefore, the music teacher works to the best of his ability. According to experts, the performance skills and experience of famous singers and musicians belonging to several generations in status performance have led to the rise of this field. In this case, the composer and performer who has reached the level of master tries to make his contribution to the eternalization of classical music samples by "infecting" his students with his creative talent. Following this rule, the students should further polish the scientific and creative skills they received from their teachers and in turn try to pass them on to the representatives of the next generation. each class of the people composed tunes according to their nature. One of these classes was young children and delicate people, that is, women. For this people, it is said in the work, they created a song so that this people can also enjoy it. Because among all the weights, there is no more pleasant weight than Taronadin. At the end of the 19th century and in the first half of the 20th century, Benazir Hafiz and musician Abdulaziz Rasulov, one of the great successors of the traditions of maqam performance, used to show young singers who learned maqam different versions of the same song in order to improve the creative skills of his students, and taught them to improvise independently. In this way, the teacher demanded from his students to achieve creative perfection. Based on the "Master-Disciple" school, the study of statuses was formed in the distant past and is

continued until now. Performing arts lessons have traditionally been taught in a mentor-student format. Each student was under the supervision and education of his teacher. Singing, singing, correct pronunciation of words, understanding the meaning of poems and ghazals, studying musical heritage are always under the supervision of teachers. The student's independent singing in front of the public and music lovers was done with the direct permission of the teacher. It is necessary to retrain music teachers who do not have singing practice in special courses, to develop their skills. The time itself demands to conduct serious research. In cooperation with the Teacher Retraining Institute and the Republican Education Center, the "School of Skills" seminars are regularly held, where some issues encountered in school textbooks are reviewed. In conclusion, the art of music, like all areas of social life, cannot progress without enjoying the priceless heritage of the ancestors. Therefore, staying true to traditions and relying on them at every moment is the guarantee of the future fruit, children's prospects and the upbringing of a well-rounded generation.

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